

MODELING THE FILAMENT WINDING PROCESS

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Summary

A model is presented which can be used to determine the appropriate values of the process variables for filament winding a cylinder. The model provides the cylinder temperature, viscosity, degree of cure, fiber position and fiber tension as functions of position and time during the filament winding and subsequent cure, and the residual stresses and strains within the cylinder during and after the cure. A computer code was developed to obtain quantitative results. Sample results are given which illustrate the information that can be generated with this code.

Introduction

Filament winding has been employed successfully in constructing small fiber reinforced composite cylinders. Unfortunately, recent attempts to filament wind large cylinders have met with less success. Manufacturers have found it difficult to produce large cylinders with reproducible and acceptable quality.

The reason for faulty products often lies in the manufacturing process, namely, in the filament winding and subsequent curing. Presently the process variables are selected empirically and this does not ensure that all the process variables have the appropriate values. The shortcomings of the empirical approach could be overcome by an analytical model. A model which provides the process variables needed to produce filament wound cylinders is described in this paper.

Filament Winding Process

During the filament winding process a composite shell is formed by winding resin-coated fibers onto a mandrel rotating at an angular velocity ω (Fig. 1). The principal steps of the manufacturing process are summarized below.

Winding. A cross-head feeds bands of fiber bundles through a resin bath and onto a mandrel of radius R , while maintaining a tension F_o per unit bandwidth in these bundles. The cross-head moves back and forth on a path parallel to the mandrel axis with a speed V . The absolute values of ω and V determine the rate at which the shell's thickness is built up, while their ratio controls the winding angle ϕ , which corresponds to the orientation of the fibers in each layer.

At this stage two material phases, the solid fibers and the soft resin, co-exist in the shell. While the resin remains "soft", the fibers can move away from their initial position, changing the fiber distribution and fiber tension.

Figure 1 Description of the problem.

Aging. After the winding is complete, the shell, with its mandrel, is sometimes stored at room temperature. During such storage, chemical reactions may occur which affect the composition of the material.

Curing. The shell and mandrel are placed in a heated oven. The chemical reactions which take place during the cure determine the cylinder's final properties. The mandrel and the shell also expand during the cure, giving rise to stresses and strains within the shell.

Post-curing. The solidified composite shell is often returned to the oven one or more times for such steps as stress relief, loading of propellant, secondary bonding of stiffeners and liners. The matrix is cured further (postcured) by the additional heating.

As can be seen from the above, the process variables we have direct control over are

- a) mandrel geometry
- b) mandrel angular velocity
- c) cross head speed as a function of its position
- d) initial fiber tension
- e) cure, and postcure temperatures

It is desired to establish a model which provides the following information as functions of position and time

- | | |
|-------------------|-------------------------|
| a) temperature | d) fiber position |
| b) degree of cure | e) fiber tension |
| c) viscosity | f) stresses and strains |

In the following sections we present a model which relates the above parameters to the process variables.

Analysis

The cylinder is considered to be a thin cylindrical shell of length L whose thickness is uniform along the axial and circumferential directions. This thickness varies with time during the manufacturing process. The mandrel's internal structure is represented by a thin hollow cylinder with an "effective" thickness which is constant in time (Fig. 1). Any temperature or stress edge effects at the ends of the shell and the mandrel (located at $x = \frac{L}{2}$ and $x = -\frac{L}{2}$) are neglected; every property is taken to vary only along the radial direction.

Within the overall description of the filament winding process given in the previous section, it is possible to distinguish several phenomena. These are the curing reactions taking place in the composite matrix, the unbalanced forces acting on the fibers, and the thermal deformations being experienced by the shell. Consequently, the problem can be subdivided into the following three models

- a) the thermochemical model which provides the temperature, viscosity and rate of cure, and determines the degree to which the shell has cured,
- b) the fiber motion model which provides the fiber tension and fiber movement, and determines the fiber's positions,
- c) the stress model which provides the "hardened" composite's stresses and strains.

The fiber motion and stress models are coupled to the thermochemical model through the material properties and thermal deformations which occur during the curing process. Thus, while these models are established separately, they are to be solved concurrently.

The thermochemical model is based on the analysis developed by Springer and Loos for the curing of prepreg tape [1,2], but was extended to include the accumulation of fibers with time that takes place during winding. The fiber motion and stress models were developed from first principles for this specific application.

Thermochemical Model

The thermochemical model describes the thermal and chemical processes which occur inside the shell during the complete manufacturing cycle (filament winding, aging, curing, and postcuring) and takes into account the increase in wall thickness during winding. The thermochemical model, built on the ideas developed for prepreg tape by Springer and Loos [1,2], is not described here in detail. Only the main features of the model are given, highlighting the changes in the Springer-Loos model necessitated by the time varying wall thickness.

As in the case of prepreg tape, the model starts with the energy equation

$$\frac{\partial(\rho CT)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\kappa \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) + \rho \dot{H} \quad (1)$$

where t is time, r is the radial coordinate, T is the temperature, \dot{H} is the rate at which heat is generated or absorbed by chemical reactions, ρ is the density, κ is the thermal conductivity, and C is the specific heat of the composite.

From Springer and Loos' definition of the degree of cure α

$$\dot{H} = \left(\frac{d\alpha}{dt} \right) H_r \quad (2)$$

where $\frac{d\alpha}{dt}$ is the rate at which the cure is proceeding and H_r is the total heat of reaction.

The applicable initial and boundary conditions are as follows. The initial temperature and degree of cure of the material as it is added to the shell being wound is

$$T = T_o \quad ; \quad \alpha = \alpha_o \quad \text{at} \quad t = t_o \quad (3)$$

where T_o is the temperature of the material (which is generally the same as the temperature of the room where it is being dispensed T_a) while α_o is the degree of cure the resin has acquired before it is deposited on the shell.

The boundary conditions are

$$T = T_s \quad \text{at} \quad r = R + h_s \quad (4)$$

$$T = T_m \quad \text{at} \quad r = R - h_m \quad (5)$$

where T_s is the temperature of the shell's outer surface, T_m is the temperature at the mandrel's inner surface, and h_s is the sum of the instantaneous thicknesses of all the layers that have been wound up to time t . The temperature T_s frequently approximates the ambient room temperature T_a . Note that T_s , T_m and h_s may vary with time, while h_m , which is the effective thermal thickness of the mandrel, remains constant throughout the manufacturing process.

To complete the definition of this problem, an expression is needed which provides a relationship between the rate of cure $\frac{d\alpha}{dt}$, the degree of cure α , and the temperature T . A relationship in the form $\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = f_1(\alpha, T)$ is given in [3].

In addition to the above system of equations, expressions are needed relating the thermal conductivity κ and the thermal heat capacity per unit volume $C' = \rho C$ to the degree of cure α and the temperature T . The chosen approximate expressions are [4]

$$\kappa = f_2(\alpha, T) = \alpha\kappa^c + (1 - \alpha)\kappa^{uc} \quad (6)$$

$$C' = f_3(\alpha, T) = \alpha C'^c + (1 - \alpha)C'^{uc} \quad (7)$$

where the superscripts c and uc refer to the properties of the cured ($\alpha = 1$) and uncured ($\alpha = 0$) states.

Equations (1) to (7) define the model. Solutions to these equations provide the temperature and the degree of cure as functions of position and time. From this information the viscosity μ can also be determined, provided a relationship of the form $\mu = f_4(\alpha, T)$ is known. A procedure for establishing such a relationship is discussed in [3].

Fiber Motion Model

Bands of fiber bundles are wound under tension F_0 per unit bandwidth to create each layer of the shell. The curvature imparted to the fiber bundles by the mandrel results in a force N_r acting on the fibers in the radial direction. As long as the matrix has not yet "hardened", these forces induce fiber movement. The fiber motion is resisted by a drag due to the motion of the fiber relative to the resin. In the following a model is developed which provides

- a) the position of any fiber bundle,
- b) the tension in each fiber bundle,
- c) the fiber volume ratio at any point within the shell at any point in time.

The following assumptions are adopted in the model

- a) The resultant of all the forces acting on an element of the fiber bundle is always oriented in the radial direction.
- b) Accelerations and decelerations in the fiber motion are so small that the inertial forces are negligible.
- c) All the fiber bundles in a given layer start moving at the same time from the same initial position. This assumption implies that the entire layer appears instantaneously in its place at the designated time t_0 . This is a reasonable assumption because the time required to wind each layer is generally negligible compared to the total time involved in winding the entire shell [4].

- d) Resin flow parallel to the mandrel surface is negligible both in the shell's circumferential and axial directions.

The equilibrium of forces for any given fiber bundle is

$$P_r + P_d = 0 \quad (8)$$

where P_r is the radial force per unit area resulting from the fiber tension and the local curvature, and P_d is the total drag force per unit area that the fiber bundle experiences. This drag corresponds to a pressure drop in the fluid (resin) across the fiber bundle

$$P_d = -\Delta P \quad (9)$$

Given the high fiber volume fraction, the composite can be idealized as a porous medium. Thus the viscous flow giving rise to ΔP can be represented by Darcy's law [5]

$$\Delta P = \mu \left(\frac{h_f}{S} \right) \dot{w} \quad (10)$$

where μ is the viscosity of the matrix, \dot{w} is the velocity of radial motion, S is the apparent permeability and h_f is the effective thickness of the fiber bundle.

In this model all of the fiber material in a layer is considered to be concentrated in a solid "fiber sheet" encapsulated within the layer's resin (Fig. 2). Since the volume of the fibers remains constant during the manufacturing process, the effective thickness of the fiber sheet is fixed and is defined as

$$h_f = V_{f_0} \Delta z_0 \quad (11)$$

where V_{f_0} is the initial fiber volume fraction and Δz_0 is the initial layer thickness.

Figure 2 Cross section of the mandrel and the shell side.

The radial position of the fiber sheet can be defined as

$$r = R_0 - w \quad (12)$$

where R_0 is the fiber bundle's initial radius of curvature ($t = t_0$) and w is the radial distance between the fiber bundles' initial and present position (Fig. 2). The initial radius R_0 is the sum of the mandrel's outer radius R and the thicknesses of all the layers present at time $t = t_0$.

Curvature in a fiber bundle can be caused by winding on the cylindrical surface of the mandrel, and by winding around the curved ends of the mandrel. Consequently we write

$$P_r = (P_r)_I + (P_r)_{II} \quad (13)$$

where $(P_r)_I$ is the radial pressure component resulting from the radial force $(N_r)_I$ due to the fiber tension in the fiber bundles wrapped around the circumference of the mandrel (Fig. 3a). $(P_r)_{II}$ is the radial pressure that results from the radial force $(N_r)_{II}$ due to the tension in the fiber bundles wrapped around the ends of the mandrel (Fig. 3b). From Fig. 3 we have

$$(P_r)_I = \frac{F}{r} \sin^2 \phi \quad (P_r)_{II} = 2 \frac{F}{L} \cos \phi \sin \frac{\Theta_d}{2} \quad (14)$$

where F is the instantaneous tension per unit width of the fibers, ϕ is the layer's winding angle, and Θ_d is the layer's dwell angle.

Figure 3 The forces due to winding around the circumference (Figure a, top) and the ends (Figure b, bottom) of the mandrel.

The relationship between the instantaneous position of the fiber and its tension requires some hypothesis about the fiber's behavior. In this model we postulate that the fibers resemble thin, linearly elastic wires. This postulate results in the following expression for the fiber tension [4]

$$F = E \left[\left(\frac{R_o - w}{R_f} \right) - (1 + \epsilon_T) \right] h_f \quad (15)$$

where E is the elastic modulus of the fiber, which is considered to be independent of temperature, R_f is the radius of curvature at which there is no tension in the fiber, and ϵ_T is the fiber's thermal strain at its present temperature. The chosen thermal strain law is

$$\epsilon_T = \beta_f (T - T_s) \quad (16)$$

where β_f is the thermal coefficient of expansion of the fiber. The reference temperature T_s is the temperature of the first layer at the start of the winding process ($t = 0$).

As for R_f , it can be expressed in terms of the fiber bundle's initial position, tension and thermal strain, quantities which are known. These initial conditions are

$$F = F_o ; \quad r = R_o ; \quad w = 0 ; \quad \epsilon_T = \epsilon_{T_o} \quad \text{at } t = t_o \quad (17)$$

Substitution of eq. (17) into eq. (15) yields

$$R_f = \frac{R_o}{\frac{F_o}{Eh_f} + \epsilon_{T_o} + 1} \quad (18)$$

where ϵ_{T_o} is the fiber's thermal strain at the temperature T_o at which it was added to the shell.

By substituting eqs. (9), (10), and (12) through (15) into eq. (8) and neglecting higher-order terms, the following fiber motion equation is obtained

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{w} + \left(\frac{ES}{\mu} \right) \left[\frac{R_o}{R_f} \left(\sin^2 \phi + 4 \frac{R_o}{L} \cos \phi \sin \frac{\Theta_d}{2} \right) - (1 + \epsilon_T) \left(2 \frac{R_o}{L} \cos \phi \sin \frac{\Theta_d}{2} \right) \right] \frac{w}{R_o} = \\ \frac{ES}{\mu R_o} \left[\frac{R_o}{R_f} - (1 + \epsilon_T) \right] \left(\sin^2 \phi + 2 \frac{R_o}{L} \cos \phi \sin \frac{\Theta_d}{2} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Solutions to equation (19) provide the instantaneous position of each fiber bundle and the tension in each bundle. From the known position of each fiber bundle, the fiber volume fraction in each layer can then readily be determined.

The fiber motion problem has now been completely determined. In solving this equation the resin viscosity at the instantaneous location of the fiber bundle must be known. The average resin viscosity in a layer can be calculated by the thermochemical model. The calculations require a knowledge of the position of the fiber bundles in each layer, a layer being defined by its cylindrical inner and outer boundary surfaces. The resin mass

in any layer contained between these two surfaces always remains the same. However, as time progresses, the position of the boundaries between two adjacent layers may change for either of two reasons

- a) The resin density changes during the cure. Shrinkage of the resin near the mandrel surface moves the remainder of the resin mass closer to the mandrel.
- b) Fiber bundles move through the resin. As fibers move towards the mandrel, resin is displaced away from the mandrel.

During the calculations we must keep track of the position of each resin layer boundary and the positions of the fiber bundles relative to these boundaries.

Stress Model

Once the shell has hardened, thermal stresses and deformations are introduced in it. These stresses and strains are caused by temperature changes within the shell and by the forces exerted on the shell by the mandrel as it undergoes thermal expansion.

The shell's layup may or may not be symmetric. However, even for a symmetric layup there may be an "effective unsymmetry" caused by asymmetrical temperature or degree of cure distributions. Owing to the shell's complexity and to the presence of interlaminar shear the problem can not be analyzed by simple laminated plate theory [6]. Instead, a more general set of equations had to be developed for obtaining the stresses and strains in the shell as functions of position and time.

In establishing these equations the following assumptions were made

- a) Normal stresses in the radial direction are negligible when compared to the inplane stresses [7].
- b) Bending and buckling of the shell is prevented by the presence of the elastic mandrel, with which the shell is always in positive contact.
- c) Each individual layer is orthotropic and linearly elastic.

The problem is to calculate the components of the stress and strain vectors in each layer (Fig. 4)

$$\vec{\sigma} = \{ \sigma_x, \sigma_\theta, \tau_{xr}, \tau_{r\theta}, \tau_{\theta x} \} \quad \vec{\epsilon} = \{ \epsilon_x, \epsilon_\theta, \gamma_{xr}, \gamma_{r\theta}, \gamma_{\theta x} \} \quad (20)$$

where σ and ϵ denote the normal stress and strain components in the direction specified by their subscript, and τ and γ denote the shear stress and strain components in the planes specified by their subscripts.

Note that assumption (b) above removes the possibility of bending, which usually introduces out-of-plane shear into the shell [8,9]. Nevertheless, the out-of-plane shear components are retained in eq. (20) because of the need to accommodate the asymmetry mentioned at the beginning of this section.

The general procedure used to establish this model's governing equations is outlined in the remainder of this section. Regretfully, due to the length of this analysis and to the space limitations imposed by these Proceedings we cannot cover all the details here. Readers interested in additional depth are referred to [4].

The governing equations are obtained through the Reissner functional, an energy formulation, defined below as $U^n + V^n$. The procedure is to obtain the first variation of

Figure 4 Illustration of the stress components in a layer element.

this functional with respect to each of the unknowns grouped in the vector $\vec{\Omega}$ to be defined later, and equate it to zero [10]

$$\delta_{\vec{\Omega}}(U'' + V'') = 0 \quad (21)$$

where U'' is the shell's strain energy and V'' the potential energy of the mandrel-shell interface forces. Equation (21) yields a state of stress and strain corresponding to static equilibrium and compatible deformations.

The appropriate form of the strain energy U'' is the following volume integral [10]

$$U'' = \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{z_k}^{z_{k+1}} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_{-\frac{L}{2}}^{+\frac{L}{2}} [(\sigma_x)_k \varepsilon_x + (\sigma_\theta)_k \varepsilon_\theta + (\tau_{xr})_k \gamma_{xr} + (\tau_{r\theta})_k \gamma_{r\theta} + (\tau_{\theta z})_k \gamma_{\theta z} - F_k'] (R_{ref} + z) dx d\theta dz \quad (22)$$

where k is the layer index number which counts outward from the mandrel, and z_k and z_{k+1} are the radial coordinates respectively defining the layer's inner and outer boundary surfaces (Fig. 3). The radial distance z is measured from the laminate's midsurface. The radius of curvature of this surface is

$$R_{ref} = R + \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{\Delta z^k}{2} \quad (23)$$

The complementary energy density F_k' is defined as [10]

$$F_k' = \int_0^{(\sigma_x)_k} \varepsilon_x d\sigma_x + \int_0^{(\sigma_\theta)_k} \varepsilon_\theta d\sigma_\theta + \int_0^{(\tau_{xr})_k} \gamma_{xr} d\tau_{xr} + \int_0^{(\tau_{r\theta})_k} \gamma_{r\theta} d\tau_{r\theta} + \int_0^{(\tau_{\theta z})_k} \gamma_{\theta z} d\tau_{\theta z} \quad (24)$$

In order to be able to integrate the above expression, the stress-strain relations for

the materials in the shell must be known. In this analysis it is assumed that they can adequately be described by Hooke's law, since the strains and rotations are expected to be small. The material description is further simplified by assuming that each layer is orthotropic in its principal material axes. Thus, the stress-strain law becomes [6]

$$\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_\theta \\ \gamma_{xr} \\ \gamma_{r\theta} \\ \gamma_{\theta x} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{S}_{11}^k & \bar{S}_{12}^k & 0 & 0 & \bar{S}_{16}^k \\ \bar{S}_{21}^k & \bar{S}_{22}^k & 0 & 0 & \bar{S}_{26}^k \\ 0 & 0 & \bar{S}_{44}^k & \bar{S}_{45}^k & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \bar{S}_{54}^k & \bar{S}_{55}^k & 0 \\ \bar{S}_{61}^k & \bar{S}_{62}^k & 0 & 0 & \bar{S}_{66}^k \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_\theta \\ \tau_{xr} \\ \tau_{r\theta} \\ \tau_{\theta x} \end{bmatrix}_k + \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{T_x} \\ \varepsilon_{T_\theta} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \gamma_{T_{\theta x}} \end{bmatrix}_k \quad (25)$$

where \bar{S}_{ij} is the compliance matrix in shell coordinates, and ε_T and γ_T are the normal and shear strain components, respectively, of the thermal strain vector. These matrix and vector elements are functions of winding angle and temperature, as well as material properties, as shown in refs. [4,6].

As mentioned previously, the external forces acting on the composite shell are due to differences in the thermal expansions (or contractions) of the shell and the mandrel. In this model the mandrel is assumed to be made of a linearly elastic material. The mandrel is then represented by a spring "foundation" on the shell's inner surface and by extensional restraint springs at its edges, as shown in Fig. 5. Therefore, for the present problem, the potential energy of the forces acting on the shell's boundaries V'' can be expressed as [4]

$$\begin{aligned} V'' = & \int_0^{2\pi} \left\{ \int_{z_1}^{z_{N+1}} \left(\frac{K_z}{1 + \frac{K_z}{K_e}} \right) \left[\frac{(\Delta L - u(\frac{L}{2}))u(\frac{L}{2}) - (\Delta L + u(-\frac{L}{2}))u(-\frac{L}{2})}{2} \right] dz \right. \\ & + \int_{-\frac{L}{2}}^{\frac{L}{2}} K_r [C_f(\Delta R + w_1)(u_R + v_R) + (\Delta R + \frac{w_1}{2})w_1] dx \\ & \left. + \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{z_k}^{z_{k+1}} \int_{-\frac{L}{2}}^{\frac{L}{2}} \left[\left(\frac{F_h^k}{\Delta z^k} + E_{11} \frac{\varepsilon_{11}}{2} \right) \varepsilon_{11} \right] dx dz \right\} R d\theta \quad (26) \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\varepsilon_{11} = (u_1 \cos^2 \phi_k + 2v_1 \cos \phi_k \sin \phi_k + \frac{w_1}{R_{e,f}} \sin^2 \phi_k) + (u_2 \cos^2 \phi_k + 2v_2 \cos \phi_k \sin \phi_k) z \quad (27)$$

Figure 5 Model of the shell-mandrel interactions during thermal deformations, showing the spring constants and deflections for the edge connections (Figure a, right) and for the elastic foundation (Fig b, left).

$u(\frac{L}{2})$, $u(-\frac{L}{2})$ and w_1 are the unknown axial and radial displacements of the shell's boundary surfaces, and u_R and v_R are the axial and circumferential displacements of the shell at the shell-mandrel interface. F_h^k is the k -th layer's fiber tension at hardening. E_{11}^k is the elastic modulus of the fiber bundles in the k -th layer. ΔL and ΔR are the amounts by which the mandrel's principal dimensions would change in the axial and radial directions, respectively, if it was not constrained by the composite shell [4].

$$\Delta L = \epsilon_{T_x} L = [\beta_m(T - T_m)]L \quad \Delta R = [\beta_m(T - T_m)]R \quad (28)$$

where β_m is the mandrel's thermal coefficient of expansion and T_m is the mandrel's temperature at the start of winding ($t = 0$). C_f is Coulomb's coefficient of friction at rest for the shell-mandrel interface surface, K_x and K_r are the effective axial and radial spring constants of the mandrel, and K_e is the spring constant representing an elastic connection between the shell and the mandrel at the edges. The mandrel spring constants K_x and K_r are functions of the mandrel's dimensions and its material properties [4]

$$K_x = \frac{2E_m}{L} \quad K_r = \frac{E_m h_m}{R^2} \quad (29)$$

The value of K_e varies, depending on how the fiber bundles are handled when the cross-head reaches the end of its travel and starts the return pass. Its lower bound is $K_e = 0$, which represents the absence of any mechanical connection between the shell and the mandrel at both ends. Its upper bound is $K_e = \infty$, which represents a rigid edge joint.

Solution is approached through what is known as the direct method. The method involves proposing a set of stress and displacement distributions in space and time. These trial functions are to approximate the solution we seek. These distributions are constructed by the linear superposition of simpler functions. For this particular case, the following linear forms are assumed for the stresses [11]

$$\begin{aligned} (\sigma_x)_k &= (J_x^0)_k \sigma_x^0 + (J_x^1)_k \sigma_x^1 z \\ (\sigma_\theta)_k &= (J_\theta^0)_k \sigma_\theta^0 + (J_\theta^1)_k \sigma_\theta^1 z \\ (\tau_{xr})_k &= (J_{xr}^0)_k \tau_{xr}^0 + (J_{xr}^1)_k \tau_{xr}^1 z \\ (\tau_{r\theta})_k &= (J_{r\theta}^0)_k \tau_{r\theta}^0 + (J_{r\theta}^1)_k \tau_{r\theta}^1 z \\ (\tau_{\theta x})_k &= (J_{\theta x}^0)_k \tau_{\theta x}^0 + (J_{\theta x}^1)_k \tau_{\theta x}^1 z \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

where J^i is the stiffness ratio factor of order i for the layer ($i = 0, 1$). The stiffness ratio factor depends on the material and the layup (see Appendix). The weighting coefficients σ^i and τ^i are the unknowns to be determined.

For the displacements, the following linear forms are assumed

$$\begin{aligned} u &= (u_1 + u_2 z)x \\ v &= (v_1 + v_2 z)x \\ w &= w_1 \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

where u , v and w are the displacements under load along the axial, circumferential and

radial directions, x is the axial distance from the shell's midsection. $u_{1,2}$, $v_{1,2}$ and w_1 are unknown weighting coefficients to be determined from the model's governing equations.

By applying the relationships between strains and displacements given in ref. [12], eq. (31) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_x &= u_1 + u_2 z \\ \epsilon_\theta &= w_1 / R_{ref} \\ \gamma_{xr} &= u_2 x \\ \gamma_{r\theta} &= v_2 x \\ \gamma_{\theta z} &= v_1 + v_2 z \end{aligned} \tag{32}$$

As a result of eqs. (30) and (32) the vector of unknowns $\vec{\Omega}$ can now be defined as follows

$$\vec{\Omega} = \{ \sigma_x^o, \sigma_x^1, \sigma_\theta^o, \sigma_\theta^1, \tau_{xr}^o, \tau_{xr}^1, \tau_{r\theta}^o, \tau_{r\theta}^1, \tau_{\theta z}^o, \tau_{\theta z}^1, u_1, u_2, v_1, v_2, w_1 \} \tag{33}$$

Substitution of eqs. (22), (24) through (27), (30) and (32) into eq. (21) yields a set of 5 linear algebraic equations with 5 unknowns for equilibrium, and a set of 10 linear algebraic equations with 10 unknowns for compatibility. Simultaneous solution of these systems of equilibrium and compatibility equations for the values of the elements of $\vec{\Omega}$ produces all the information needed to determine the stresses in and deformations of the shell at any time.

Solution

Solutions to the thermochemical, fiber motion, and stress models must be obtained by numerical means. Algorithms were developed which are suitable for numerical solutions of the models. These algorithms were implemented by a computer code designated as WIND. The output (results) provided by the code is given in Table I.

Table I. Output Produced by the Solution of the Thermochemical, Fiber Motion and Stress Models

- (1) temperature as a function of radial position and time $T(r, t)$
- (2) average degree of cure for each layer as a function of time $\alpha(t)$
- (3) average viscosity of each layer as a function of time $\mu(t)$
- (4) radial distance of each fiber bundle from the outer surface of the mandrel as a function of time $d(t)$
- (5) average tension per unit width in each fiber bundle as a function of time $F(t)$
- (6) in-plane normal and shear stresses $\sigma_x(r, t), \sigma_\theta(r, t), \tau_{\theta z}(r, t)$
- (7) out-of-plane shear stresses $\tau_{xr}(r, t), \tau_{r\theta}(r, t)$
- (8) in-plane normal and shear strains $\epsilon_x(r, t), \epsilon_\theta(r, t), \gamma_{\theta z}(r, t)$
- (9) out-of-plane shear strains $\gamma_{xr}(x, r, t), \gamma_{r\theta}(x, r, t)$
- (10) case length as a function of time $L(t)$
- (11) shell mid-surface radius as a function of time $R_{ref}(t)$
- (12) shell wall thickness as a function of time $h_s(t)$
- (13) fiber volume fraction of each layer as a function of time $V_f(t)$
- (14) thickness of each layer Δz

Discussion

Sample results were generated to illustrate the type of information provided by the thermochemical, fiber motion and stress models. In the examples we considered a shell being wound on an Alcoa 6061-T6 aluminum mandrel. This mandrel was taken to be 4 meters (157.5 in) in diameter and 8.5 meters (334.65 in) in length.

The speed at which the cross-head traversed was set at 82.42 mm/sec (3.245 in/sec) and the angular velocity was set at 0.02914 rad/sec (0.2783 rpm), resulting in a 45° winding angle. Each fiber band was taken to be 150 mm (5.9 in) wide. These parameters resulted in a dwell angle of 167° [13]. Each layer was assumed to be made of 0.1651 mm (0.0065 in) thick Hercules AS/3501-6 graphite composite (49.3 percent fibers by volume). These parameters were kept constant until a total of 14 layers had been wound, corresponding to a shell thickness of 2.31 mm (0.091 in).

The material properties used in the calculations were extracted from the published data on Hercules AS/3501-6 graphite-epoxy composites and Alcoa 6061-T6 aluminium alloy [13,14].

The temperatures of the outer surface of the case and of the inner surface of the mandrel were taken to be the same as the ambient temperature, which was held constant at 25° C (77° F).

The temperature, degree of cure and viscosity in each ply were calculated as the layers were wound on the mandrel. These calculations showed that, as expected for the unheated cylinder, the temperature remained nearly constant across the shell and mandrel, at a value equal to the ambient temperature. Hence, the temperatures are not plotted here. However, the degree of cure and viscosity changed with radial position and time. The degree of cure and viscosity of the innermost ply, as a function of time, is shown in Fig. 6. The variations of the degree of cure and viscosity across the shell's thickness at different times after the start of the winding are shown in Fig. 7.

Figure 6 The degree of cure and viscosity of the innermost layer as a function of time.

Figure 7 The variation of the degree of cure and the viscosity across the filament wound cylinder wall at different times elapsed from the start of the winding process.

Figure 8 The positions of different fiber sheets relative to the mandrel surface as a function of time.

Figure 9 The circumferential normal stress σ_θ , the inplane shear stress $\tau_{\theta z}$, the axial ϵ_x and circumferential ϵ_θ normal strains in the filament wound cylinder after cure. The innermost layer is designated as the first layer ($k = 1$).

The positions of different fiber sheets relative to the mandrel surface are shown in Fig. 8. In this figure the starting point for each layer is the time t_o at which the layer was added to the cylinder.

The stresses and strains in the shell were also calculated by assuming that during cure the case underwent a 150° C (270° F) temperature change. The circumferential normal stress σ_θ and the inplane shear stress $\tau_{\theta z}$ in each layer are given in Fig. 9. The remaining stress components were practically zero. The axial and circumferential normal strains, ϵ_x and ϵ_θ , in each layer are also shown in Fig. 9. The remaining strain components were negligible.

The computed stresses and strains are nearly uniform across the cylinder because of the geometry used chosen for these sample calculations. For other conditions, there may of course be large variations in stresses and strains across the cylinder, which the model would also predict.

The aforementioned examples (Figs. 6-9) illustrate the results which can be generated by the model. These sample calculations were performed for simple conditions to demonstrate the main features of the models. However, the model and the corresponding WIND code can be used to generate similar information for complex filament winding problems of practical significance.

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Appendix: Derivation of Stiffness Ratio Factors

The stiffness ratio factor concept allows us to formulate the stresses in each layer in terms of averaged laminate stresses at the midsurface. In this Appendix we present expressions for the stiffness ratio factors applicable to our stress model.

To formulate the stiffness ratios we need the generalized Hooke's law for an orthotropic material, which is [6]

$$\vec{\sigma}_k = [\bar{Q}]_k \vec{\epsilon} \quad (34)$$

where $[\bar{Q}]_k$ is the reduced stiffness matrix for layer k . The force per unit width vector resulting from the integration of the above layer stress vector through the laminate thickness

is

$$\bar{N} = [A]\bar{\varepsilon}^{(0)} + [B]\bar{\varepsilon}^{(1)} \quad (35)$$

where $\bar{\varepsilon}^{(0)}$ and $\bar{\varepsilon}^{(1)}$ are the zero and first order strain vectors. For the definition of the elements of the $[A]$ and $[B]$ matrices see [6] or any laminated composite structures text.

The zeroth order stiffness ratio factors for the k^{th} layer, as developed by Arnold and Mayers [11], are

$$(J_x^0)_k = \frac{(\bar{Q}_{11})_k h_s}{A_{11}} \quad (J_\theta^0)_k = \frac{(\bar{Q}_{22})_k h_s}{A_{22}} \quad (36a, b)$$

$$(J_{xr}^0)_k = \frac{(\bar{Q}_{44})_k h_s}{A_{44}} \quad (J_{r\theta}^0)_k = \frac{(\bar{Q}_{55})_k h_s}{A_{55}} \quad (J_{\theta z}^0)_k = \frac{(\bar{Q}_{66})_k h_s}{A_{66}} \quad (36c, d, e)$$

In what follows we develop the appropriate first order stiffness ratio factors for our problem. To derive the first order stiffness ratio factor in the shell axis direction x , the applied stress and the resulting strain are assumed to be

$$\bar{N} = \frac{1}{12} \{ \sigma_x^1 h_s^2, 0, 0, 0, 0 \} \quad \bar{\varepsilon} = \{ z \varepsilon_x^1, 0, 0, 0, 0 \} \quad (37)$$

where z is the radial coordinate.

Substitution of eq. (37) into (36) yields

$$\varepsilon_x^1 = \frac{\sigma_x^1 h_s^2}{12 B_{11}} \quad (38)$$

Equations (35) and (38) yield

$$(\sigma_x)_k = z (\bar{Q}_{11})_k \varepsilon_x^1 = z \frac{(\bar{Q}_{11})_k h_s^2}{12 B_{11}} \sigma_x^1 = z (J_x^1)_k \sigma_x^1 \quad (39)$$

Hence, the first order stiffness ratio factor, for the k^{th} layer, is

$$(J_x^1)_k = \frac{(\bar{Q}_{11})_k h_s^2}{12 B_{11}} \quad (40a)$$

The other first order membrane stiffness ratio factors can be obtained by similar procedures. The results are

$$(J_\theta^1)_k = \frac{(\bar{Q}_{22})_k h_s^2}{12 B_{22}} \quad (40b)$$

$$(J_{xr}^1)_k = \frac{(\bar{Q}_{44})_k h_s^2}{12 B_{44}} \quad (J_{r\theta}^1)_k = \frac{(\bar{Q}_{55})_k h_s^2}{12 B_{55}} \quad (J_{\theta z}^1)_k = \frac{(\bar{Q}_{66})_k h_s^2}{12 B_{66}} \quad (40c, d, e)$$